

Dynamic Mechanical Properties of Raffia Palm Fibre/Groundnut Shell Particulate Reinforced Epoxy Hybrid Composites

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ABSTRACT

The dynamic mechanical properties of raffia palm fibre and groundnut shell particulate/epoxy (RPF/GSP/E) hybrid composites have been studied using dynamic mechanical analyser (DMA). Raffia palm fibres and groundnut shell particulates were treated with 10 % NaOH solution at room temperature. The hybrid composite was produced by hand lay-up method with varying weight percentages (10, 20, 30, 40, and 50) reinforcements of raffia palm fibre and groundnut shell particulate in the ratio of 1:1. Dynamic mechanical tests were performed in terms of storage modulus (E'), loss modulus (E''), damping ($\tan \delta$) and glass transition temperature (T_g) at different frequencies of 2, 5 and 10 Hz. The results indicated that, thermal stability and load bearing capacity was found to improve with increase in fibre loading in the composites. In addition, it was also observed that variation in frequencies had a significant effect on dynamic mechanical properties of (RPF/GSP/E) composites; the storage modulus of the samples ranged from 180-2900 MPa, storage modulus shifts to higher values at higher frequencies. The glass transition temperature (T_g) of the composite varied from 37 °C to 72 °C, also shifted towards higher temperatures for higher frequencies. The hybrid composite can be used as interior panel of automobiles and in making the casing of electronics such as mobiles, laptops and Television.

Key words: Dynamic mechanical properties, Hand lay-up method, Epoxy resin, Raffia palm fibre, Groundnut shell particulate

INTRODUCTION

The production of high performance engineering materials from renewable resources is one ambitious goal currently being pursued by researchers across the globe. For environmental and ecological concern, natural fibre reinforced polymer composites may be better alternative of synthetic fibre reinforced polymer composite due to low cost, low density, biodegradability, recyclability, availability and acceptable mechanical properties of the natural fibres. Currently, natural fibre reinforced polymer composites have been widely used materials in many applications such as automobile, electronics, packaging and construction industries [1].

In recent years, natural fibres has been used to produce hybrid composite with improved mechanical properties. Hybrid composites are materials made by combining two or more different types of fillers in a single matrix. Hybridization of two types of fibres can offer some advantages over using each of the fibres alone in a single polymer matrix; this provides flexibility to the design engineer to tailor the material properties according to particular requirements [2]. From available literature it has been found that, Raffia palm fibre has high tensile strength [3]. It has also, been reported that, addition of groundnut shell particulate to polymer composites, increase thermal stability as well as the glass transition temperature of the composites [4]. Therefore, a hybrid of raffia palm fibre/groundnut shell particulate will produce a composite that will have sufficient mechanical properties as well as good thermal stability suitable for some automobile and electronic applications.

Dynamic mechanical analysis (DMA) can be described as applying an oscillating force to a composite sample and analysing the material's response to that force under the influence of frequency and temperature. Thermal properties such as storage modulus, loss modulus, damping and glass transition temperature of these composites can be easily and accurately obtained by DMA [5]. The glass transition temperature is an important output parameter of DMA, defined as a point where materials change from glassy to rubbery state, can be obtained from either peak of loss modulus or $\tan \delta$ curve [6].

As the fibre reinforced materials undergo various types of dynamic stresses during service, studies on their viscoelastic properties are of great importance. Polymeric materials exhibit viscoelastic behaviour which means that they simultaneously possess both solid-like as well as liquid-like characteristics [7]. The degree to which the polymer exhibits more solid-like or liquid-like properties is dependent upon temperature as well as time or frequency. The dynamic properties of polymeric materials are of considerable practical significance, particularly if they are determined over a wide range of frequency and temperature.

[1] studied the effect of variation in frequencies on dynamic mechanical properties of Jute fibre reinforced epoxy composites at varying frequencies of 1, 2, 5 and 10 Hz. The results indicated that thermal stability and load bearing capacity was found to improve with increase in fibres loading in the composites. Glass transition temperature and load bearing capacity were found maximum for jute composite having 30 % fibre content. On increasing the frequencies, storage modulus was found to increase and hence higher value of storage modulus was found at higher frequency in rubbery region. The highest peak of damping was found at 1 Hz frequency but on increasing the frequencies it was found to reduce. Glass transition temperature/thermal stability was also found to reduce with increase in frequencies.

The dynamic mechanical analysis of hybrid composites produced by resin transfer moulding was studied by [8], the research was aimed at evaluating the performance of glass/sisal hybrid composites focusing on dynamic mechanical analyses (DMA). Hybrid composites with different fibre loadings and different volume ratios between glass and sisal were studied in detail. The research findings showed that, the storage and loss modulus decreased with the increase in temperature, which is associated with a softening of the matrix at higher temperatures. The storage modulus increased with increasing fibre loading and this was due to the reinforcement effect imparted by the fibres which are more rigid than the matrix. The loss modulus curves were found to distribute over a wider range and reach higher peak values for higher fibre content. These curves, which are indicative of the dissipated energy, were found to be shifted to higher positions following the incorporation of more glass fibres into the composites. The incorporation of glass fibres also caused a broadening of the loss modulus peak which was attributed to the inhibition of the relaxation process within the composites. The higher loss modulus at the relaxation temperature was associated with an increase in internal friction which enhances energy dissipation. There was a shift in the glass transition towards higher temperatures on increasing the overall fibre loading and the glass fibre content. This is because of restrictions imposed on the mobility of the polymer molecules at the interface. The glass transition temperature increased with increasing frequency of the analysis due to the dephasing response of the composite at higher frequencies.

[9] studied the dynamic mechanical analysis of banana fibre reinforced polyester composites with special reference to the effect of fibre loading, frequency and temperature. At lower temperatures (in the glassy region), the E' values were found to be maximum for the unreinforced polyester whereas at temperatures above T_g , the E' values were found to be maximum for composites with 40 % fibre loading, indicating that the incorporation of banana fibre in polyester matrix induces reinforcing effects appreciably at higher temperatures. The study also found that, the maximum improvement in properties is observed for composites with 40 % fibre loading, which is chosen as the critical fibre loading. Increase of frequency shifts the T_g to higher temperatures supporting the good fibre/matrix interaction. At 40 % loading, the loss modulus peak gets broadened emphasizing the improved fibre/matrix adhesion. Moreover, an additional peak occurs at high fibre loading in the $\tan \delta$ curves, due to the interlayer effect. Addition of fibres lowers the $\tan \delta$ peak height, which again points to the improved fibre/matrix adhesion. The glass transition temperature is shifted positively on the addition of fibres.

In this work, epoxy based hybrid composite was produced with raffia palm fibre and ground nut shell particulate as the reinforcing materials. To reduce the effect of moisture absorption of natural fibres and improve dynamic mechanical properties, the fibres were treated with 10 % NaOH solution to improve the surface properties and provide better adhesion with the matrix. Alkaline treatment of cellulosic fibres with sodium hydroxide is a well-known method which has been employed to improve fibre-polymer matrix interfacial bonding [10]. This treatment reduces the hydrophilicity of the fibres and increases its hydrophobicity by the removal of natural fats and waxes from cellulosic fibre surfaces.

Dynamic mechanical properties of polymeric materials not only depends upon temperature and frequency but also on used polymeric matrices, strength and stiffness of fibres, fibre loading, fibre length, fibre orientations and adhesion between fibres and matrix.

MATERIALS

Epoxy resin: Araldite LY-556 and Hardener: (2-aminoethylethane-1, 2 diamine) HY 951 were obtained from Lagos, Nigeria. Raffia palm fibres and groundnut shells were obtained locally from Ikov, Ushongo local government area of Benue State, Nigeria. Sodium hydroxide (NaOH), distilled water, wax, hand gloves and Acetone were obtained from Makurdi, Benue State, Nigeria. The equipment used include: Set of standard laboratory Sieves and dynamic mechanical analyser.

METHODS

- A. The groundnut shells were collected from a groundnut processing centre in Ushongo local government area of Benue state, Nigeria. Cleaned and dried groundnut shells were initially washed with distilled water to remove the sand and other impurities. The washed shells were sun dried and ground. The shell particles were treated using alkali treatment method by soaking the clean groundnut shell particles in 10 % NaOH solution for 2 hours

at room temperature and then were washed with distilled water. The washed shells were again dried under the sun. The particles were sieved through standard test sieve to get 300 μ groundnut shell particles.

- B.** The raffia palm fibres were collected from raffia palm trees around Chia-Aku stream at Ikov, in Ushongo local government of Benue State, Nigeria. The pinnate leaves of the raffia palm were pulled out from the leaf stalks. Thereafter, the raffia fibres were taken off from the pinnate leaves. The fibres were washed thoroughly and allowed to dry under the sun. The raffia palm fibres were treated using alkali treatment method by soaking the clean raffia palm fibres in 10 % NaOH solution for 1 hour at room temperature. The fibres were then washed thoroughly in plentiful of distilled water to remove the excess NaOH (or non - reacted alkali). The fibres were again sun dried and cut into short fibre lengths of 10 mm to avoid fibre entanglement during production of the composite.

Production of Hybrid Composite

The production of the composite was carried out by simple hand lay-up method. A wooden mould of size 200 \times 150 \times 5 mm³ was used for casting the composite laminate. A mould release agent (wax), was first applied on all the surfaces of the mould, and allowed to dry. A thin film was formed on the mould when the wax dried. The thin film formed acts as the mould release agent. Raffia palm fibres of length 10 mm were laid in the mould by hand.

The epoxy resin and hardener were mixed in the ratio of 4: 1 by weight. These were thoroughly mixed in a plastic container. Measured quantities of groundnut shell particulate were added in the plastic container and the mixture was again stirred for 15 minutes and thoroughly mixed before it was poured into the mould. The fibres in the mould were saturated with resin that was already mixed with groundnut shell particulate, and then were rolled using a roller to ensure good contact and freedom from porosity, and the produced composite was finally cured. The closed mould was kept under a load of 25 kg at room temperature for about 24 hours before the composite was removed from it. The composite was then post cured in air for 27 days at room temperature. The produced composite is shown in Figure 1.

The composites were produced with 10, 20, 30, 40, and 50 % reinforcements of raffia fibre and groundnut shell particulate in the ratio of 1:1. Samples were designated as A, B, C, D, and E respectively. Specimens of suitable dimensions were cut for dynamic mechanical testing. Utmost care was taken to maintain uniformity in the samples.

Fig. 1 Produced Composite Laminate (5 mm thickness)

Dynamic Mechanical Analysis (DMA) Testing

The dynamic mechanical analysis was conducted using dynamic mechanical analyser(model, NETZSCH DMA 242E). The test was conducted according to ASTM D5023 three point bending test procedure. A sample size of 60 mm \times 12 mm \times 5 mm as shown in Figure 2 was placed between two supports in the furnace of the DMA machine; while the sample was heated, it was forced to oscillate by means of a loading nose midway between the supports at fixed frequency loadings of 2 Hz, 5 Hz, and 10 Hz. The machine was set to a temperature sweep between 30 $^{\circ}$ C and 180 $^{\circ}$ C, The dynamic amplitude was set at 60 μ m. In the process the material's response in form of storage modulus, loss modulus and damping parameters were displayed and monitored on the computer monitor of the machine.

Fig. 2 DMA Test Specimens

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Dynamic mechanical analysis (DMA)

The results of the dynamic mechanical analysis of the produced composite materials are presented in Figures 3-8. Table 1, shows a summary of the results of the DMA of RPF/GSP/E composite.

Storage modulus (E')

The storage modulus describes the ability of a material to support a load, and thus represents the sample's elastic component. The modulus indicates how well a material will work in specific application in the real world. For example, if a polymer is heated so that it passes through its glass transition and changes from glassy to rubbery, the modulus will often drop drastically. This drop in stiffness can lead to serious problems if it occurs at a temperature different from expected [11, 12].

Figures 3-8 show the variations in the storage modulus (E') with temperature for the various composite loadings at different frequencies of 2, 5 and 10 Hz. From the results of the experiment, it is observed that, the storage modulus ranged from 180–2900 MPa. The results of the storage modulus showed that, as the temperature increases, storage modulus (E') decreased for all the samples. This can be attributed to the increase in the molecular mobility of the polymer chains at higher temperatures. As for all composites materials, these variations correspond to a material transition. Similar results were observed by [8, 13] that, as the temperature increases, E' decreases for all composites materials.

The curves of the storage modulus clearly exhibit frequency dependence as seen from the Figures, higher frequencies gave higher storage modulus values. According to [8], modulus measurements performed over a short time (high frequency) result in higher values and on the other hand, if the reverse is done, it results in lower modulus values. On varying the oscillation frequency, changes occur in E' of composites.

A prominent increase in storage modulus of the matrix in the elastomeric region with the incorporation of fibres is expected due to an increase in stiffness of the matrix with the reinforcing effect imparted by the fibres. There is a clear increase in storage modulus (E') with fibre loading when compared to the control sample. The maximum E' values were found for the sample with 10 % fibre loading. This may be associated with the strong fibre/matrix interaction [6, 14]. The storage modulus decreased with 20 and 30 % fibre loading and then increased continuously up to 50 % fibre loading. The low storage modulus values observed in 20 % and 30 % reinforced samples may be associated with poor fibre/matrix interactions. According to [9], modulus in the glassy state is determined primarily by the strength of the intermolecular forces and the way the polymer chains are packed.

The peak observed in the storage modulus of some samples preceding the glass transition temperature (T_g) according to [11], is due to a rearrangement in the molecules to relieve stresses frozen below the T_g by processing method. These stresses are trapped in the material until enough mobility is obtained at the T_g to allow the chains to move to a lower energy state.

Fig. 3 Storage modulus (E'), loss modulus (E'') and loss factor (tan delta) of unreinforced epoxy

Fig. 4 Storage modulus (E'), loss modulus (E'') and loss factor (tan delta) of 10% reinforcement of RPF/GSP

Loss modulus (E'')

The loss modulus is equivalent to the sample's viscous response, and is proportional to the dissipated energy in form of heat, by a material during one cycle of sinusoidal load. The dynamic loss modulus is often associated with "internal friction" and is sensitive to different kinds of molecular motions, transitions, relaxation processes, morphology and other structural heterogeneities [12].

Figures 3-8 show the variation in the loss modulus (E'') with temperature for the various composite loadings at different frequencies of 2, 5 and 10 Hz. From these Figures, the loss modulus increased with increasing temperature up to the glass transition temperature and then decreased in all samples. The glass transition temperature (Tg) of composite is measured from the peak of the loss modulus curve.

The loss modulus results clearly exhibit frequency dependence. The glass transition temperature of the composites shifts to higher temperatures at higher frequencies in all samples. This is in agreement with the results presented by [13, 15]. It

is observed that, 40 % loading gave the highest value of T_g (72 °C) which shows its better thermal stability than all other RPF/GSP/epoxy hybrid composites.

It can be observed that, for higher fibre content, the loss modulus curve spreads over a wider distribution and shows a higher peak. This effect can be a consequence of the inhibition/restriction of the relaxation process of the chain segments within the composites as a consequence of a higher number of chain segments upon fibre addition [8].

Fig. 5 Storage modulus (E'), loss modulus (E'') and loss factor (tan δ) of 20% reinforcement of RPF/GSP

Fig. 6 Storage modulus (E'), loss modulus (E'') and loss factor (tan δ) of 30% reinforcement of RPF/GSP

Mechanical loss factor (Damping parameters) Tan δ

Tan delta or damping is the ratio of loss modulus and storage modulus which is related to impact resistance of the materials. Damping depends upon adhesion between fibres and matrix. Poor fibre-matrix adhesion associated with higher damping and vice-versa [16]. This fact can be explained as strong fibre-matrix adhesion could reduce the mobility of polymer chains turn into reducing damping. Lower value of damping shows the good load bearing capacity of the composite [17].

The effect of damping parameters ($\tan \delta$) on RPF/GSP epoxy composites as a function of temperature at various frequencies is presented in Figures 3-8.

It was observed from the Figures that, damping factor ($\tan \delta$) increased with increase in temperature and reached a maximum in the transition region and decreases in rubbery region in all samples. According to [8] all materials exhibit a relaxation process, which is associated with the glass-rubber transition of the matrix. This relaxation process, involves the release of cooperative motions of chains between crosslinks. Below T_g damping is low because, in this region, the chain segments are in the frozen state. Hence, the deformations are primarily elastic and the molecular slips resulting in the viscous flow are low. Also, in the rubbery region, the molecular segments are quite free to move and hence damping is low and thus there is no resistance to flow.

In the control sample the variation in $\tan \delta$ with temperature at different frequencies showed a $\tan \delta$ peak height of 1.0, 1.1 and 1.1 for the frequencies of 2, 5 and 10 Hz and corresponding temperatures of 52, 55 and 59 °C.

These results showed higher temperatures corresponding to higher frequencies and higher $\tan \delta$ peak. The maximum $\tan \delta$ value observed among the samples investigated was 1.1 from the unreinforced sample as seen in Figure 3. This is an indication of better damping among all the samples investigated. The 30 % loading gave the lowest $\tan \delta$ values of 0.35, 0.40, and 0.45 corresponding to frequencies of 10, 5 and 2 Hz respectively at a temperature of 50 °C, as seen in Figure 6. This indicate better load bearing capacity of the sample. This fact may be due to strong fibre-matrix adhesion leads to effective stress transfer.

The position and height of the $\tan \delta$ peak are indicative of the structure and properties of a particular composite material. Generally, composites have considerably less damping in the transition region compared to unreinforced resin, because the fibres carry a greater amount of the load and allow only a small part of it to strain the interface.

It is observed that, the values of $\tan \delta$ for the control sample (unreinforced epoxy resin) Figure 3, were higher than the values of the reinforced epoxy composites. This is because, there is no restriction to the chain motion in the case of unreinforced matrix, while the presence of the cellulose fibres in the reinforced samples hindered the chain mobility, resulting in the reduction of $\tan \delta$ peak values of the samples. This is in agreement with [15] that fibres in composites increase the fibre/matrix interfacial bonding and acts as a barrier that restricts the mobility of chain segment; leading to reduction in damping factor in the rubbery region.

According to the results shown in this study other factors also, contribute to the softening of the interface. Generally, composites containing less fibre content, exhibit higher $\tan \delta$ peak heights as seen in figures 4 and 5 for 10 and 20 % fibre loading respectively. One reason for this may be that there is more resin by volume with less fibre content, and there is more energy at the interface because of the increase in the interfacial area. The matrix dissipates more energy than composites, because the fibres carry a greater amount of the load, dissipating a small part of it to strain the interface.

Fig. 7 Storage modulus (E'), loss modulus (E'') and loss factor ($\tan \delta$) of 40% reinforcement of RPF/GSP

The effect of frequency on viscoelastic properties of RPF/GSP/E composite

The viscoelastic properties of materials depend on the temperature and the frequency (time), and because of these, the dynamic mechanical tests were performed over a temperature range at constant frequencies of 2, 5 and 10 Hz. Any material subjected to a constant stress over a period of time, undergoes a decrease in its elastic modulus due to its

molecular rearrangement in order to minimize the localized stresses[9]. Modulus measurements performed over a short time (high frequency) result in higher values and this behaviour is seen in Figures 3-8. The storage modulus of the samples shifts to higher values at higher frequencies. The variation in $\tan \delta$ with temperature at different frequencies shows that the $\tan \delta$ peak height increases with frequency. The T_g of the composite is also shifted towards higher temperatures for higher frequencies. This is in agreement with the results of several researchers [8, 9, 13].

Fig. 8 Storage modulus (E'), loss modulus (E'') and loss factor ($\tan \delta$) of 50% reinforcement of RPF/GSP

Table -1 Dynamic mechanical properties of RPF/GSP epoxy hybrid composite at various frequencies of 2, 5 and 10 Hz.

% Loading	Frequency (Hz)	Peak height of Storage modulus (E') MPa	Transition Temperature (T_g) $^{\circ}$ C from E'' curve	Mechanical loss factor, peak height from ($\tan \delta$) curve
10	2	2900.023	68	0.70
	5	2900.023	68	0.71
	10	2900.023	68	0.72
20	2	460.012	34	0.78
	5	560.312	37.8	0.78
	10	640.443	38	0.78
30	2	190.153	39	0.45
	5	210.134	39	0.37
	10	230.011	39	0.33
40	2	1400.345	69	0.53
	5	1400.112	70	0.53
	10	1400.011	72	0.53
50	2	1300.543	42	0.51
	5	1390.342	44	0.53
	10	1400.011	48	0.55
CONTROL SAMPLE 100 % Epoxy	2	362.423	40	1.0
	5	423.332	44	1.1
	10	465.132	47	1.1

CONCLUSION

The effect of loading on the dynamic mechanical properties of RPF/GSP/E hybrid composites has been studied. It is observed that, the storage modulus decreased with the increase in temperature. The storage modulus increased with fibre loading when compared with the control sample. The results showed that, the storage modulus of the samples shifts to higher values at higher frequencies. The glass transition temperature (T_g) of the composite also shifted towards higher

temperatures for higher frequencies due to the de-phasing response of the composite at higher frequencies. The results of the dynamic mechanical analysis showed that, reinforcement actually improved the dynamic mechanical properties of the composite, 10 % loading gave the highest storage modulus of 2900 MPa and a glass transition temperature of 68 °C. And 40 % loading gave the highest glass transition temperature of 72 °C and a storage modulus of 1400 MPa. The composite material can be used for automotive interior panels as well as casing for electronics such as laptops, radios and television sets.

REFERENCES

- [1]. M Gupta. Effect of Variation in Frequencies on Dynamic Mechanical Properties of Jute Fibre Reinforced Epoxy Composites. *Journal of Materials and Environmental Sciences*. (2018).
- [2]. R Velmurugan, V Manikandan. Mechanical Properties of Palmyra/Glass Fiber Hybrid Composites. *Composite Part A – Applied Science*; (2007).38:2216–26.
- [3]. R Elenga, G Dirras, M Goma and M Bernard. On the microstructure and physical properties of untreated raffia textiles; *Composite part A: Applied science and manufacturing* (2009). 40(4), 418-422.
- [4]. G Raju, V Gaitonde, and S Kumarappa. Experimental Study on Optimization of Thermal Properties of Groundnut Shell Particle Reinforced Polymer Composites. *International Journal of Emerging Science*, (2012). 2(3), 433-454.
- [5]. M Kevin. *Dynamic Mechanical Analysis: A Practical Introduction*, 2nd edition, CRC Press. (2008).
- [6]. L Heitor, C Sandro and S Alexandre S. Mechanical and Dynamic Mechanical Analysis of Hybrid Composites Molded by Resin Transfer Molding. *International Journal of Modern Engineering Research*, (2010). 2 471-474.
- [7]. H Kishi and A Fujita, A. "Wood-based Epoxy Resins and the Ramie Fibre Reinforced Composites", *Journal of Environmental Engineering and Management*. (2008) 7, pp. 517-523.
- [8]. H Ornaghi, A Bolner, R Fiorio, A Zattera and S Amico. Mechanical and Dynamic Mechanical Analysis of Hybrid Composites Molded by Resin Transfer Molding. *Journal of Applied Polymer Science*; (2010). 118:887–96.
- [9]. L Pothan, Z Ommen and S Thomas. Dynamic Mechanical Analysis of Banana Fiber Reinforced Polyester Composites. *Composites Science and Technology*,(2003). 63: 283-293.
- [10]. G Nyior, S Aye, S Tile. Study of Mechanical Properties of Raffia Palm Fibre/Groundnut Shell Reinforced Epoxy Hybrid Composites. *Journal of Minerals and Materials Characterization and Engineering*, (2018). 2018, 6, 179-192
- [11]. P Menard. *Dynamic Mechanical Analysis: a practical introduction*. CRC Press. New York. (1999).
- [12]. M Jawaid, K Abdul, R Hassan and A Dungani. Effect of Jute Fibre Loading on Tensile and Dynamic Mechanical Properties of Oil Palm Epoxy Composites. *Composite. Part B. Eng.* (1999).45; 619–624.
- [13]. A Ekhlal. *The Mechanical Properties of Natural Fiber Composites*. A thesis submitted for the degree of Doctor of Philosophy, Faculty of Engineering. Swinburne University of Technology. (2013).
- [14]. N Hameed, P Sreekumar and B Francis. *Composite Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*. (2007). 38, 2422.
- [15]. K Pickering, M Aruan, and T Le. A review of Recent Developments in Natural Fibre Composites and their Mechanical Performance. *Journal of Composites: Part A* (83) (2016). 98-112.
- [16]. A. Hernandez, V. Santos, M. Icaza and M. Victor, *Compos: Part B*, 38 (2007) 405
- [17]. D. Shanmugam, M. Thiruchitrambalam, *Mater. Des.* 97 (2013) 533.